

THE IMPORTANCE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPING COMMUNICATIVE SKILLS IN STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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***Abstract.** Communication skills have a unique role in the preparation of competitive personnel with modern knowledge, among many fields there are necessary factors of the electronic information educational environment in the development of these skills in road engineers. In this article, the didactic tools of these factors and their importance are discussed in detail, scientific and practical instructions and recommendations are discussed.*

***Keywords:** communicative skills, electronic information, webinars, forum and chat platforms, didactic tool, virtual simulation, training and seminars, electronic textbook, video conferences, multimedia resources, virtual communication platforms.*

Modern education today requires teachers and students to be aware of all types of information technologies and have the skills to use them. Since we live in an era of complex global information exchange, this requirement is certainly inherent in the age of technology and our Honorable President Sh.M.Mirziyoev, who did not ignore this, in paragraph 2.4 of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-6079 dated October 5, 2020 on approval of the “Digital Uzbekistan - 2030” strategy and measures for its effective implementation, spoke about the priority areas of development of the national market of digital technologies, and in this regard, it was mentioned that special attention should be paid to the skills of students studying in higher educational institutions to use digital technologies and to train competitive personnel [1]. It follows that the provision of higher education institutions with digital technologies and the formation of students' skills in using these techniques is continuing consistently.

The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the wide introduction of digital technologies at all stages of the education system and increasing the level of digital knowledge necessary for a modern economy, improving the educational infrastructure, as well as opening digital knowledge training centers in all regions of the republic by 2024 within the framework of the implementation of the “Five Initiatives” project was adopted by Sh.M.Mirziyoev [2]. Also, the words of our Honorable President, who emphasized that “In order to achieve progress, it is necessary and necessary for us to master digital knowledge and modern information technologies. This will give us the opportunity to take the shortest path to progress” are certainly significant.

The development of electronic information environments in education and their use in educational processes, along with increasing students' interest in learning, is also an important factor in their development as competitive personnel.

This scientific article discusses the importance of didactic tools of the electronic information environment and the necessary factors for the development of communicative skills of students in higher educational institutions. In this regard, it is necessary to make effective use

of the achievements of foreign interactive teaching methods, further develop measures for organizing education through technologies using modern technologies.

It should not be forgotten that the creation of an electronic information educational environment, along with creating a number of conveniences for students, also imposes responsibility on them. This responsibility creates a love for their field, a desire to learn it, and prepares the ground for becoming a qualified specialist in their profession.

Electronic information educational environment - this is the use of digital platforms and tools to organize interaction between students and teachers [4]. Through this environment, educational processes can be carried out in real time or asynchronously at any stage of education. Electronic information educational environment has the following advantages for students:

Free communication: it allows for constant communication between teachers and students, which activates the exchange of knowledge and the learning process.

Faster information exchange: students have access to online lessons and can use them anytime, anywhere.

Personalized learning: an individual approach is created for each student. Electronic platforms offer educational materials according to the interests and needs of students [5].

The professional activities of higher education students require the performance of various communicative tasks. For example, project presentations, development and explanation of engineering solutions, teamwork, etc.

Didactic tools used in the electronic information educational environment help to achieve the following achievements in this regard:

Virtual simulations: Through simulation programs, students are prepared to analyze real-life problems and solve them through communication. This is especially important for developing the skills of correctly explaining technical issues and using technical terms [6].

Webinars and online classes: Through webinars, students can interact with leading experts, ask questions, and enrich their knowledge. Students can also strengthen their communication skills through mutual discussions, group projects, and working in a collaborative environment.

Forum and chat platforms: online forums and chat rooms designed for students provide an opportunity to exchange ideas and analyze their knowledge. This helps to improve written communication skills [7].

Multimedia resources: students have the opportunity to deepen their understanding of the topics they are studying through the use of video, audio and 3D graphic tools. Such tools not only provide technical knowledge, but also develop their skills in explaining and presenting it [7].

The above resources play a leading role in shaping students' communicative skills, but without didactic tools, these resources cannot be considered fully effective. Didactic tools have their place in the electronic information environment, and the following types can be analyzed:

Electronic textbooks and manuals: Higher education students are offered the necessary knowledge through specially prepared electronic textbooks. Such textbooks are enriched with interactive elements, making the learning process more interesting and effective [8].

Interactive laboratories: laboratory classes create virtual laboratories for existing subjects, where students can independently test their knowledge through their own participation, simulate various processes. This teaches them to conduct experiments and exchange ideas when analyzing the results.

Online testing and assessment systems: in the electronic information educational environment, students have the opportunity to independently assess their knowledge through online tests. This allows them to analyze their results and identify their communicative shortcomings [9].

These tools teach students to master technical knowledge, as well as to effectively apply it in the communication process. Such an approach is of great importance in improving the professional skills of students and making them competitive personnel. Thus, the widespread introduction of digital technologies into the educational process and their continuous improvement are becoming an integral part of modern education.

Every young student studying at a higher educational institution today wants to acquire modern knowledge, strengthen their skills and have sufficient qualifications in their field when they step into a big life. The high demand in the labor market in our country today for personnel who have become specialists in their field requires further strengthening the bond between the teacher and the learner in higher education and organizing work in the spirit of mutual cooperation. In particular, in the technical direction of higher education, the need for mature thinking personnel, possessing modern knowledge and being able to independently use digital technologies remains high. Meeting such requirements is a long and responsible process, and only by creating the above-mentioned electronic information environment of education can the upbringing of competitive personnel with a broad outlook, who clearly know their task, and who can make rational decisions be a worthy solution.

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